

Measuring the Effect of Ventilation on Cooking in Indoor Air Quality by Low-Cost Air Sensors

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Abstract—The concern of the indoor air quality (IAQ) has been increasing due to its risk to human health. The smoking, sweeping, and stove and stovetop use are the activities that have a major contribution to the indoor air pollution. Outdoor air pollution also affects IAQ. The most important factors over IAQ from cooking activities are the materials, fuels, foods, and ventilation. The low-cost, mobile air quality monitoring (LCMAQM) sensors, is reachable technology to assess the IAQ. This is because of the lower cost of LCMAQM compared to conventional instruments. The IAQ was assessed, using LCMAQM, during cooking activities in a University of Minnesota graduate-housing evaluating different ventilation systems. The gases measured are carbon monoxide (CO) and carbon dioxide (CO₂). The particles measured are particle matter (PM)_{2.5} micrometer (µm) and lung deposited surface area (LDSA). The measurements are being conducted during April 2019 in Como Student Community Cooperative (CSCC) that is a graduate housing at the University of Minnesota. The measurements are conducted using an electric stove for cooking. The amount and type of food and oil using for cooking are the same for each measurement. There are six measurements: two experiments measure air quality without any ventilation, two using an extractor as mechanical ventilation, and two using the extractor and windows open as mechanical and natural ventilation. The results of experiments show that natural ventilation is most efficient system to control particles and CO₂. The natural ventilation reduces the concentration in 79% for LDSA and 55% for PM_{2.5}, compared to the no ventilation. In the same way, CO₂ reduces its concentration in 35%. A well-mixed vessel model was implemented to assess particle the formation and decay rates. Removal rates by the extractor were significantly higher for LDSA, which is dominated by smaller particles, than for PM_{2.5}, but in both cases much lower compared to the natural ventilation. There was significant day to day variation in particle concentrations under nominally identical conditions. This may be related to the fat content of the food. Further research is needed to assess the impact of the fat in food on particle generations.

Keywords—Cooking, indoor air quality, low-cost sensor, ventilation.

I. INTRODUCTION

DURING the last years there has been increasing concern over the effect of indoor air quality (IAQ) [1]. Problems of indoor air quality are risk factors for human health in low, middle, and high-income countries [2]. The concentration of indoor pollution is twice compared to outdoor air pollution

[3]. This is important because Americans spend about 90 percent or more of their time indoors [4]. The smoking, sweeping, and stove and top stoves use are the activities have the major contribution to the indoor air pollution [3]. The outdoor air pollution also affects the IAQ [5]. The aspects influence in the IAQ from emission related to cooking activities are cooking methods, cooking materials, fuels, and ventilation [6].

The fuel use for cooking has significant impact on the IAQ [7]. The three main fuels use are solid, gas, and electric. The solid fuels such as coal, wood, and crop residues are used for around 50% of world's population, mainly in developing countries [8]. These types generate high concentrations of particles, carbon monoxide (CO) [9], volatile organic compounds such as benzene, toluene, and xylene [10], and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) and sulfur dioxide (SO₂) [11]. Natural gas generates high emissions of CO [12] while liquefied petroleum gas generates high emissions of NO₂ and CO as well [13]. There are no significant emissions from the stove and stovetop themselves using electricity as power supply. This is because there is no fuel combustion. This study is focus on measuring the IAQ using an electric stove and stovetops.

The deep-frying caused the largest increase in particles reaching 6.0 x 10⁵ cm⁻³ that is 24 times higher than background concentration and 90% of those particles are nanoparticles. The pan-frying, stir-frying, and boiling increase 4.4, 3.7, and 2.8 times the concentration respectively [14]. Thus, cooking by oil emits more airborne agents, such as benzene and formaldehyde, compared to cooking by water [14]-[15]. The main factors contribute to higher emission are frying, the browning of food, the presence of oil and fat, the pan temperature, and the pan type [16]. Exposure to any form of frying could increase the risk of lung cancer in nonsmoking women [17]. The exposure to cooking activities produce asthma symptoms in children [18]. Cooking activities in an electric stove produces levels of PM₁₀ levels ranged 1,200-1,300 µg·m⁻³, formaldehyde levels ranged 130-420 µg·m⁻³, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), NO₂ levels excess 400 ppb in one-hour, and CO levels ranged 1-5 ppm [19]. Benzene and formaldehyde have cancer-related health impacts [20]. The PM₁₀ EPA standard is 150 µg·m⁻³, therefore the concentrations related to emissions from cooking activities are ~ 10 times higher. Exposure to concentrations higher than 100 µg·m⁻³ provoke alveolar inflammation, with release of mediators capable, in susceptible individuals, of causing exacerbations of lung disease and of increasing blood coagulability [21]. The NO₂ EPA standard for one-hour is 100

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II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Materials

The measurements were conducted in Como Student Community Cooperative (CSCC) which is a graduate housing at University of Minnesota. The apartment has two bedrooms, one bathroom, and living room and kitchen in the same area. The kitchen and living room have an area of 77.8 m³. During the experiments, the bedrooms and bathroom doors were closed, therefore the measurement area is living room and kitchen. This is shown within the red line in Fig. 1.

ppb, thus the cooking activities produce four times concentration above this standard. NO₂ exposure causes adverse respiratory health effects, and in spaces with low air-circulation it causes severe lung injury and death [22]. Increase in 5 ppb NO₂ in 24 hour-average causes an increase of 6% in the asthma related hospital admissions in children between 5-14 years [23]. NO₂ increases of ~25 ppb in one-hour exposure is associated with 1.3% increase in the daily number of deaths [24].

The ventilation to control and reduce the air pollution concentration include hood system (mechanical) and natural ventilation that consist to open the windows nearby cooking activities [25]. The main purpose of ventilation is to create a more suitable IAQ by diluting and removing the pollutants produce [26] during cooking activities. The hood system does not remove, significantly, the air pollution [27]. The natural ventilation is more efficient, compared to mechanical system, to improve the IAQ, furthermore, both system working at the same time achieve higher remove of pollutants during cooking activities [25].

The low-cost, mobile air quality monitoring (LCMAQM) sensors, can be a feasible option to measure the air quality in a kitchen. The LCMAQM is more accessible for researchers and local governments or authorities because of its cost. The cost of typical sensors for LCMAQM are only \$150-200 each. A wireless Mobile Autonomous Air Quality Sensor box (MAAQsbox) to measure air pollution was developed. The MAAQSbox contains LCMAQM sensors (gas and particle) and a wireless broadcasting system. The LCMAQM technology has limitations. The data obtained by these sensors are less reliable compared to the data collected by sensors from an air monitoring station (AMS) [28]. Environmental conditions, mainly ambient temperature, and humidity [29] affect the output of LCMAQM sensors. Thus, there are challenges to using this sensor technology in the field where it is impossible to control temperature and relative humidity. For example, in periods of high temperatures, LCMAQM sensors diverge from the reference sensors affecting the results of measurements [30]-[34]. Also, there are cross-sensitivities of LCMAQM sensors with other gases, thus, field calibration is required to obtain valid data [30]. It was examined the quality of the LCMAQM data, by assessing the performance of MAAQSbox relative to Minnesota Pollution Control Agency AMS regulatory equipment. The calibration was conducted in the field evaluating the impact of temperature, relative humidity, and cross-sensitivity in the calculation of the concentrations.

The aims of this study are to measure the IAQ during cooking activities in a University of Minnesota graduate-housing and assess the effectiveness of both mechanical and natural ventilation systems. The measurements were conducted using LCMAQM sensors. The gases measured were carbon monoxide (CO) and carbon dioxide (CO₂). The particle measured were PM_{2.5} and lung deposited surface area (LDSA).

Fig. 1 Graduate housing at University of Minnesota

The meat used for cooking was a boneless beef top sirloin steak varying in weight from 225 to 239 grams. The meat was cooked in on the four electrical burners. The potatoes were cooked in the oven and its weight was 258 grams. The olive oil was used to fry the meat and cook potatoes. The range is an electrical Kenmore with an oven and four top-burners. The range hood is an Air-King model AD1305 that has a combination grease and charcoal odor filter. This is a ductless operation range hood.

Fig. 2 Schematic of The Mobile Autonomous Air Quality Sensor box (MAAQsbox)

B. Description of the MAAQsbox

The MAAQsbox is a device that allows for autonomous conditioning of sample streams and houses several gas and particle sensors. The MAAQsbox can function under various and extreme weather conditions. For instance, it has a system to protect the sensors during rain or high humidity. The MAAQsbox contains the sensors for detection, pumps for advecting flow through the device, a heater to control the temperature, and an Arduino for system control. As shown in Fig. 2, air flows through an impactor, removing particles larger than $10\ \mu\text{m}$. Then, a humidity sensor determines the relative humidity, giving a signal to the Arduino allowing for determination of whether it is safe to advect flow into the sensor array. Subsequently, the sample air flows through 3-way valve and heater to maintain temperature and humidity levels within desired targets. Finally, a 3-way connector distributes the air to sensor areas. The MAAQsbox holds three gas sensors and one particle sensors. The gas sensors included in the calibration are CO and O₃, B4 sensors (AlphaSense, Inc.) and CO₂ (Yoctopuse). The Partector that measures lung deposited surface area (LDSA). The PM_{2.5} were measured, externally of MAAQsbox, by SidePak.

C. Sensor Technology

The CO and O₃ gases are measured by Alphasense B4 sensors. A B4 sensor contains three main components. Each sensor contains Working, Auxiliary, Reference, and Counter electrodes [35]. The target gas diffuses through a membrane where occur electrochemical oxidation (CO) or reduction (O₃) at the working electrode, generating a current signal [34], [35]. This electric signal is balanced by the counter electrode [34], [36]. The reference electrode anchors the working electrode and helps to maintain working electrode performances and its sensitivity [36]. The auxiliary electrode is not exposed to the target gas. This is to provide the background current to the current observed in the working electrode [37]. An individual

sensor board also designed by Alphasense is used to reduce environment noise achieving good ppb or ppm resolution [34] [38].

The CO₂ sensor uses non-dispersive infra-red absorption (NDIR) [39] technology based on a SenseAir K30 module [40]. CO₂ molecule, under the influence of infrared (IR) light, absorbs the light at a specific wavelength ($4.2\text{-}4.3\ \mu\text{m}$) [41]. The number of photons absorbed is proportional to the CO₂ concentration [42].

Traditional concerns and research on particles have focused on the mass-concentration of particles [43]. However, the lung-deposited surface area may be more useful in predicting the adverse effects of particles on human health [44]. The Partector measures particles in a size range from $10\ \text{nm}$ to $10\ \mu\text{m}$ but the measurement is weighted to approximate the product of particles surface area and inhaled deposit fraction in the alveolar region of the respiratory system [45]. The Partector is not considered LCMAQM sensor because its cost is $\sim \$5,000$, but this device is still considerably cheaper than other ultrafine particle measurement equipment.

The SidePak Personal Aerosol Monitor AM510 is a belt mounted laser photometer [46]. The aerosol stream passes through an impactor which removes particles larger than $2.5\ \mu\text{m}$. Smaller particles continue with the stream into the optical chamber, where they are illuminated with a focused beam of laser light at a wavelength of $670\ \text{nm}$ [47]. This sensor is a light scattering detector [48]. The size range of measurement is between $0.3\text{-}10\ \mu\text{m}$ [49].

D. MAAQsbox Field Calibration

The aim of the field calibration was to evaluate low-cost sensor performance compared to a reference instruments in the field. AMS provide robust data of the air pollution. Thus, the LCMAQM sensors were installed next to an AMS to compare its results with the low-cost sensors. This field calibration was conducted for CO and O₃, gas sensors. The calibrations of

LCMAQM sensors were determined by multivariate linear regressions (MLR). The CO and O₃ sensors presented R² values of 0.95 and 0.79 respectively. The standard error (SE) for CO was 0.04 and for O₃ was 5. The fit improved when the temperature and humidity were included. The field calibration was conducted for 244 hours. The SidePak and the CO₂ sensor were run using factory calibration. The AMS does not measure CO₂.

TABLE I
 CALIBRATION RESULTS OF B4 GAS SENSORS

Sensor	N	R ²	SE
CO	244	0.95	0.04
O ₃	244	0.79	5

E. Measurements and Statistical Analysis

1) Measurements

There were three different experiments and each experiment was conducted twice. This is to assess the consistency between the measurements under same ventilation conditions. The windows were opened one hour before beginning each measurement. The steady conditions in terms of concentration were CO₂ less than 450 ppm, PM_{2.5} less than 6 µg·m⁻³, and LDSA less than 2 µm²·cm⁻³. The inside humidity varied between 32%-46% and temperature between 23°-24°C. Once the steady conditions were achieved the windows were closed and the measurements begun 10 minutes after this. 23 minutes later, the potatoes were put in the oven at 176°C and 5cc of olive oil. In the first experiment everything was maintained in the same condition, that is windows were kept closed and no extractor was used. In the second experiment the extractor was turned on this time, but the windows were kept closed. In the third experiment the extractor was turned on and windows were opened (EWO). Three minutes after the potatoes were put in the oven, the pan was on the burner with 5cc of olive oil at level 5 where 1 is the lowest and 9 is the highest; four minutes later the meat was put in the pan. After 11 minutes of cooking, the pan power was reduced to 3. Then, after 10 more minutes the oven and burner were turned off. The measurements continued for 25 minutes after this. The total time of measurement was 76 minutes.

2) Statistical Analysis

The signals of CO, O₃, and CO₂ sensors were read by an Arduino. In the same way, humidity, rain, water sensors, and valve positions are read by another Arduino board. All data from both Arduino boards were sent to Yocto-Serial. The data from Partector were read by Yocto-RS232. The data were stored in each Yocto-Board and then the data were retrieved one time per day. The data for PM_{2.5} were storage in the SidePak. The statistical analysis was performed by assessing the concentration by second and averaging the data per minute. The data are presented comparing the three experiments with different ventilation conditions. The data analysis was conducted by Matlab, R, and Excel. Ozone and carbon monoxide were both very low and not influenced significantly by cooking and will not be further discussed.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figs. 3-5 are plots and LDSA, PM_{2.5}, and CO₂ against time for the three different experimental conditions. Individual data points are shown along with best fit lines associated with the model described below. The average LDSA concentration during the measurements without mechanical and natural ventilation is 16 µm²·cm⁻³ and with mechanical ventilation(extractor) is 15 µm²·cm⁻³. Using EWO, the concentration achieved is 6.9 µm²·cm⁻³. The average PM_{2.5} concentrations are also higher without ventilation compared to using the extractor. The concentrations without ventilation and using the extractor are 13 µg·m⁻³ and 11 µg·m⁻³ respectively. Using EWO, the average PM_{2.5} concentration is 7.4 µg·m⁻³. Thus, it would seem the extractor had minor influence on LDSA and PM_{2.5} concentrations, while as expected opening the window significantly reduced them.

In order to understand what was happening in the kitchen in more detail, we model the kitchen as a simple well stirred vessel with sources and sinks. Taking LDSA as an example, let *s* be concentration of LDSA in the kitchen that has a total volume of *V* so that the total LDSA surface area in the room is *S* = *sV*. The rate of increase of surface area in the room is the difference between surface addition and removal rates.

$$\dot{S}_{in} - \dot{S}_{out} = \frac{dS}{dt} = V \frac{ds}{dt}$$

$$\dot{S}_{out} = \dot{Q}s + A_w V_d s = Ks$$

$$K = \dot{Q} + A_w V_d$$

here *K* is the total loss coefficient and consists an effective ventilation rate, *Q_v*, and the rate of particle deposition to the walls, the product of the total wall surface area of the kitchen, *A_w*, and particle deposition velocity, *V_d*.

$$\dot{S}_{in} = V \frac{ds}{dt} + Ks$$

$$\frac{\dot{S}_{in}}{V} = \frac{ds}{dt} + \frac{K}{V}s$$

Then let $C = \frac{\dot{S}_{in}}{V}$ = the rate surface area, LDSA, is added to the kitchen by cooking divided by the total room volume and $\frac{K}{V} = \frac{1}{\tau}$ where τ is the combined wall and effective ventilation loss time constant, then:

$$C = \frac{ds}{dt} + \frac{s}{\tau}$$

This is a first order linear differential equation the general solution of which is:

$$s = A + B e^{\left(\frac{-t}{\tau}\right)}$$

Then if *s* = *s₀* at *t* = *t₀* we can solve for *A* and *B*, *A* = *Cτ* and *B* = *s₀* - *Cτ*, and

$$s = C\tau + (s_0 - C\tau)e^{\frac{-(t-t_0)}{\tau}}$$

We have used this model to examine the measurements of LDSA, PM_{2.5} and CO₂. Fitted trends and shown in the figures and fitted parameters are summarized in Table II.

TABLE II

WELL STIRRED VESSEL FIT PARAMETERS. THE TOTAL ROOM VOLUME WAS 77.8 M³, TOTAL ROOM WALL SURFACE AREA 73.9 M², EXTRACTOR FLOW RATE 7.1 M³/MIN

LDSA	C [μm ² /s]	τ [min]	K [m ³ /min]	Vd [cm/s]	h _c	Q win [m ³ /min]
No vent	8.5E+06	31.8	2.4	0.055		
Extractor	9.9E+06	22.9	3.4	0.055	0.135	
Window	6.8E+06	8.3	9.4	0.055	0.135	6.0
Average	8.4E+06					
PM _{2.5}	dPM _{2.5} /dt [mg/s]	τ [min]	K [m ³ /min]	Vd [cm/s]	h _c	Q win [m ³ /min]
No vent	1.6E+00	115.0	0.7	0.015		
Extractor	1.8E+00	65.1	1.2	0.015	0.073	
Window	2.3E+00	11.8	6.6	0.015	0.073	5.4
Average	1.9E+00					
CO ₂		τ [min]	K [m ³ /min]			Q win [m ³ /min]
Windows		9.6	8.1			8.1

In Fig. 3 we see that the LDSA begins to rise rapidly shortly after meat is added to the pan with the fit indicating formation rates ranging from 6.8 to 9.9·10⁶ μm²/s. The rise in LDSA stops almost immediately when the heat is reduced, but exponential decay does not start until the range and oven are turned off. Decay time constants are strongly dependent on conditions decreasing from 31.8 to 22.9 to 8.3 minutes for no vent, extractor, and extractor plus window respectively as the loss coefficient K increases from 2.4 to 3.4 to 9.4 m³/min. If we assume that for the no vent case losses are entirely due to wall deposition, this corresponds to an average deposition velocity of 0.055 cm/s. When the extractor is turned on, K increases by 1.0 m³/min to 3.4 m³/min. If we assume this does not change wall losses significantly, the efficiency of removal of LDSA by the extractor is the ratio of the incremental removal rate of 1.0 m³/min to the extractor flow rate of 7.1 m³/min, 13.5%. When the window is opened K increases to 9.4 m³/min. Thus, the effective ventilation rate by the window is 6.0 m³/min. The details are shown in Fig. 3.

As shown in Fig. 4, PM_{2.5} behaves somewhat differently from LDSA in that for the no vent and extractor cases the rate of increase does not decrease when heat is reduced. Consequently, the model was fit to the entire heating period. On the other hand, in the window open case the concentration peaked shortly after the end of the high heat period, so the model was fit to the high heat period. In Table II, we see that formation rates calculated from the model ranged from 1.6 to 2.3 μg/s, averaging 1.9 μg/s. Decay time constants were longer ranging from 115 to 11.8 min. and corresponding loss coefficients lower compared to the LDSA case. Using the same assumptions as for the LDSA case gives a deposition velocity of 0.015 cm/s, extractor efficiency of 7.3%, and effective window ventilation rate of 5.4 m³/s.

Fig. 3 Lung Deposited Surface Area plotted against time for the three experimental conditions, measured data and fit lines shown. Red dotted/dashed lines indicate the start of heating the followed by putting the meat in the pan, green dotted/dashed lines indicate, reduction of burner heat, followed by turning off heating element and oven

LDSA is primarily a measure of ultrafine particles, mainly below 100 nm while PM_{2.5} particle mass is mainly found above about 100 nm. Alvin [50] did a detailed study of deposition velocities on indoor walls in turbulent flow and found that deposition velocity decreased with increasing particle size in the range from 10 nm to 1 μm, consistent with our observation of lower deposition velocity for the larger PM_{2.5} particles compared to LDSA particles. However, they reported lower deposition velocities than we have observed here, with values no higher than 0.01 cm/s, even for very small 10 nm particles. This suggests that the losses we observed in the no vent case were not only due to wall losses but included some ventilation unaccounted for.

Filtration efficiency typically increases with decreasing particle size below about 300 nm diameter [51] so the higher extractor efficiency observed for LDSA compared to PM_{2.5} would be expected. On the other hand, turning on the extractor may increase other losses, so our results are likely upper estimates.

As shown in Fig. 5, CO₂ was not influenced by cooking or the extractor. For the no vent and extractor cases there was a steady slow increase in CO₂ in the room as a result of the two occupants. When the window was opened CO₂ followed an exponential decay back to ambient levels. The decay time constant was 9.6 min. corresponding to a ventilation rate of 8.1 m³/min, about 25% higher than additional effective ventilation rates observed for LDSA and PM_{2.5}.

There are differences between measurements under the same conditions, specifically for particles. The LDSA concentration for all experiments before cooking were steady, ranging 0.8-1 μm²·cm⁻³. The concentration between minute 30 and 51 for the no ventilation first experiment was 23.2 μm²·cm⁻³ while for the second one was 31.6 μm²·cm⁻³. In the same condition, PM_{2.5} concentration also presented difference. The concentration between minute 30 and 51 for the no

ventilation first experiment was $10.7 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ while for the second one was $14.5 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$. These differences were 30% for LDSA and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ measurements. This is shown in Figs. 6 (a) and (b). The CO_2 differences between minute 30 and 51 in the two experiments with no ventilation was 41 ppm which represent 5%.

Fig. 4 $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ plotted against time for the three experimental conditions, measured data and fit lines shown. Red dotted/dashed lines indicate the start of heating the followed by putting the meat in the pan, green dotted/dashed lines indicate, reduction of burner heat, followed by turning off heating element and oven

Fig. 5 CO_2 plotted against time for the three experimental conditions, measured data and fit lines shown. For the window case, window was opened 23 minutes after start, other conditions as in Fig, 3 and 4

The concentration between minute 30 and 51 for extractor first experiment was $34 \mu\text{m}^2\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ while for the second one was $22 \mu\text{m}^2\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$. In the same condition, $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentration also presented difference. The concentration between minute 30 and 51 for extractor first experiment was $14.9 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ while for the second one was $9.2 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$. These differences were 43% for LDSA and 47% for $\text{PM}_{2.5}$. This is shown in Figs. 6 (c) and (d). The CO_2 differences between minute 30 and 51 in the two experiments with extractor was 59 ppm that

represented 8%.

The LDSA concentration between minute 30 and 51 for EWO first experiment was $21 \mu\text{m}^2\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ while for the second one was $14.4 \mu\text{m}^2\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$. In the same condition, $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentration between minute 30 and 51 for the EWO first and second experiments were 11.1 and $11.9 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ respectively. These differences were 38% for LDSA and 7% for $\text{PM}_{2.5}$. The CO_2 differences between minute 30 and 51 in the two experiments with EWO was 27 ppm that represents 5%.

With EWO, all the differences between measurements under same conditions were lower compared to no ventilation and extractor. The different concentrations between first and second experiment with no ventilation may be explained because the meat in the second experiment was 7 grams heavier. However, for extractor and EWO the meat was heavier for the second experiment, but the concentrations were lower. The information of the fat percentage was available only for the whole meat and not for each piece. Other studies show that the percent of fat in the meat is a key factor that explain higher or lower concentrations under same conditions [52], [53]. Thus, the difference between measurements conducted under the same conditions might be explained by the percentage of fat of each piece of meat.

IV. CONCLUSION

The Mobile Autonomous Air Quality Sensor box was used to measure indoor air quality in a small kitchen during meal preparation. Under the conditions these experiments were conducted, opening the window, the natural ventilation, is the most efficient system to control and improve the IAQ. This result is consistent with other studies [25], [27]. However, as Minnesota average low temperature during winter range -4.3°C to -13.6°C using natural ventilation as an option to improve the IAQ is limited.

A simple well stirred vessel model has been used to help examine LDSA and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ formation and decay rates. Particle formation rates varied somewhat day to day, ranging from 6.8 to $9.9 \cdot 10^6 \mu\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ for LDSA and from 1.6 to $2.3 \mu\text{g} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ for $\text{PM}_{2.5}$. With the windows open, time constants for particle removal were short, 8.3 and 11.8 minutes for LDSA and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$, respectively.

Although average LDSA and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentrations were only slightly reduced by using the extractor, removal rates were significantly increased. It reduced removal time constants from 32 to 23 minutes for LDSA and from 115 to 65 minutes for $\text{PM}_{2.5}$. Higher removal rates, shorter time constants, for LDSA compared to $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ are consistent with LDSA being weighted toward smaller particles than $\text{PM}_{2.5}$. Fundamental particle physics predicts increasing deposition and filtration efficiencies with decreasing particle size in the submicron size regime. Others have reported that more than 90% of particles generated in the kitchen are smaller than 100 nm [54].

Fig. 6 Particle differences between measurements under same conditions

Average LDSA indoor concentrations have been reported to be 70% of outdoor, however during cooking LDSA concentrations can be higher [55]. The average and maximum LDSA concentrations measured here during cooking without ventilation were 24 and 44 $\mu\text{m}^2\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$, respectively. These are in the same range or slightly lower compared to outdoor concentration measured in cities such as Barcelona [56], Basel [57], and Lisbon [58] with 37, 30, and 62 $\mu\text{m}^2\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$, respectively.

During the experiment without ventilation the average $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ was 16 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ and the highest was 23 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$. The ambient average daytime $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ level in Minneapolis is 10 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ and the highest 1-hour concentration is 28 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ [59]. The $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ EPA standard for 24-hours is 35 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$.

CO_2 is an indicator of the occupancy pattern [60]. There were two adults in the room during the experiments. During the experiments without ventilation and with the extractor there was a nearly linear increase of CO_2 concentration with time increasing from about 480 to nearly 1000 ppm. Neither the cooking (it was an electric stove) nor the extractor had a significant impact on the concentration. On the other hand, when the window was opened the concentration quickly returned to ambient with a time constant of 9.6 minutes corresponding to a ventilation rate of 8.1 $\text{m}^3\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$.

The model results are based, in each case, no vent, extractor, and window on the average of two days testing for each condition. This may mask some of the variability. As described above there was significant day to day variation in

particle concentration. This may be related to the fat content of the meat, which has been identified as a key factor in particle formation by cooking. Further research in which fat content of the food being cooked is systematically varied would be useful.

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